

Playing Technique and its Classification in the Process of Teaching Students to the Sport of Volleyball

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Abstract:

The article shows the stages, methods and means of teaching volleyball lessons through ways to achieve high efficiency.

Keywords: methodical teaching, professional skills, elementary teaching technology, technical training of a volleyball player, action-game skills, teaching process, vocational training, dictation, demonstration and explanatory methods.

INTRODUCTION.

Volleyball differs from other sports games in its essence, content and nature. Volleyball is played on a relatively small rectangular 18 × 9-meter field divided equally in two from the middle. Modern volleyball is incredibly rich in various game skills and tactical combinations, passing with tremendous intensity and speed. Consequently, the above-mentioned peculiarities of volleyball require a perfectly improved technical skill from players. In competitive games, the wider the technical skill and the more perfectly formed in relation to external influences, the more it will be possible to win.

A game technique is a specialized set of moves or actions that are executed simultaneously in sequence and in a specific target order. Game technique should be designed to perform the movement accurately, quickly, lightly, in accordance with the situation, at a high efficiency with low effort.

The term "technique" is a Greek (tehnus) word that is used in a very broad sense and means the concept of "art" in Uzbek. Every 4 years from 776 BC, participants in the general-Greek festive

competitions in honor of God Zeus, held in the village of Olympus, at the foot of the Olympus mountains in Greece, showed their art (technique) in 2-wheel carriage racing, punching, pentathlon. Interestingly, one of the conditions of this competition was that each participant before the competition was able to demonstrate his age, muscle formation and other sensations related to this sport. Therefore, as a result of practicing a particular sport, all the organs of a person's stature, muscles and the totality of an organism are formed, consequently, the technical skill, improvement of the art of the athlete is ensured.

The technique of the game of volleyball consists of a complex of action methods necessary to carry out the game. The technique of actions is assessed by purposeful, effective action in various situations. The execution of each technical method in the game is made up of a moving system that is inextricably linked with each other. Motion techniques are dynamic and kinematic characteristics of motion that are necessary and sufficient to solve motion tasks by a particular method (a certain consistency of forces, consistency between certain parts of the body, etc).

The main part of the technique is the most important and decisive part of the main mechanism in a particular movement. The execution of the main part of the technique is represented by a large effort at a relatively short time interval.

The detail of the technique is a secondary feature that does not violate the basic mechanism of movement. The details of the technique vary in different athletes, which will depend on their morphological and functional capabilities.

When performing technical actions, certain phases of actions are distinguished in terms of time. Typically, three phases of action can be defined: preparatory, basic, and closing phases.

The importance of the preparatory phase is to create favorable conditions for performing the movement in the main phase. These conditions are created by running, jumping, performing circular movements (when setting an obstacle, inserting a ball into the game, giving an attack kick). The actions in the main phase will focus directly on solving the main action tasks. From a biodynamic point of view, the most important thing in this phase is the effective use of driving forces in the appropriate situation, in the appropriate direction.

The movements in the closing phase fade or brake sharply in order to maintain the balance of the torso. Since volleyball is a very dynamic game, a volleyball player must master various technical techniques, be able to choose them based on the playing situation and do it quickly, accurately. This determines the player's technical skill.

Signs of high technical skill are represented by:

- accurate and effective execution of movement methods;
- stability of the execution of actions in the presence of halal factors (fatigue, negative effects of external conditions) ;
- selection of response movements depending on the opponent's movements, rebuilding them and being able to control the movement parts in this;
- reliability of execution of methods.

In different periods of volleyball development, the methods, requirements, shape, content of performing technical actions change and improve. The main reason for the change in technical methods is the change in the rules of the game, the improvement of tactical actions, the growing level of physical fitness of players. The increase in the dynamics of the game in attack and defense, the increase in action potential, the expansion of the arsenal of combinations in attack and defense will also be an impetus for updating or rebuilding technical methods. Even so, it cannot be said that the methods used in the game technique have no more effective options. The functional and

physical capabilities of qualified athletes provide an opportunity to introduce new, advanced techniques into the game technique and make it a reality. Classification of Game techniques is the division of them into certain groups and sections, depending on the form, content, what the methods used are intended for, the interdependence of actions, the kinematic and dynamic structure of actions. Volleyball techniques are divided into two large sections: offensive and defensive techniques. In turn, the above sections are also divided into several groups according to the form and content of technical methods. Each group will have its own methods of execution of technical actions.

The analysis of the literature recorded on the topic allows us to recognize this fact that as a result of the scientific work on the description of modern volleyball and the classification of Game techniques, it was noticeable among schoolchildren engaged in volleyball that the work on theoretical knowledge given about the sport of volleyball was not at a satisfactory level. At the same time, it can be observed that as a result of conversations with upperclassmen, there was also no positive response to verbal requests for the classification of Game techniques.

Judging from the above, it is possible to insist that the necessary attention should be paid to the theoretical aspects of not only volleyball, but also other sports. Of course, it is advisable if, in addition to having adequate physical, technical and tactical training, theoretical training is also involved.

Through the above scientific work, we will focus on all aspects of the sport that we will recognize as modern volleyball in the future, continue the scientific work on which it is more expedient to teach volleyball techniques to start with the detail in the education of the younger generation, strengthening the necessary knowledge about the classification of volleyball techniques, while giving young people

Of course, much of the knowledge that is being done about the sport of volleyball is the qualification work we have carried out.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг «Жисмоний тарбия ва спорт тўғрисида»ги Қонуни (янги таҳрири). Тошкент, 26-май 2020 йил.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасида жисмоний тарбия ва спортни янада такомиллаштириш ва оммалаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида қарори. ПФ-5924-сон 24.01.2020.
3. L.R.Ayrapetyans, A.A.Pulatov “Voleybol nazariyasi va uslubiyati” Toshkent 2011 yil.
4. M.K.Mahmudov, F.A.Narzullayev “Sport va harakatli o‘yinlarni o‘qitish metodikasi (Voleybol). Buxoro. “Durdona” nashriyoti 2019 yil. 65-67 betlar.
5. Juraevich M. J. Actual problems of teaching physical culture in schools //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). 2020. – T. 9. – №. 11. – C. 181-187.
6. Azimovna F. M., Ashrapovich N. F. Motivation of students to do sports as part of physical education classes //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 1446-1450.
7. Azimovna F. M. Formation of spiritual and moral values of pupils in physical education lessons //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – T. 9. – №. 11. – C. 99-103.
8. Azimovna F. M. Formation of spiritual and moral values of pupils in physical education lessons //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – T. 9. – №. 11. – C. 99-103.
9. Rakhmonov Rauf Rasulovich Distribution of training loads at the stage of competitive preparation for middle runners // Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 10.5958/2249-7137.2021.00376.1

10. Сабирова Н. Р. Значение физической культуры в современном обществе //Проблемы педагогики. – 2020. – №. 6 (51).
11. Akmalovich D. B. et al. Psychological impact of football games to the formation of individuality of the student //Journal of Critical Reviews. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 466-469.
12. Nematovich K. S. The possibilities of physical culture in the modern youth internet community //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 11. – С. 177-180.
13. Murodov J. Мамлакатимизда хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасида олиб борилаётган ижтимоий-иқтисодий ислохатлар кўлами //Архив научных исследований. – 2020. – №. 29.